

PREPARATION OF 2 : 4-DICHLOROPHENOXYACETIC ACID (2:4-D)

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Two different methods of preparation of 2:4-D are reported. The first method consists in the nuclear chlorination of the phenoxyacetic acid by the action of dichlorocarbamide, prepared in a modified way. The other method consists in the conversion of phenol into 2 : 4-dichlorophenol through the different stages of nitration, reduction, diazotisation and then coupling with cuprous chloride. The 2 : 4-dichlorophenol, thus obtained, is then converted into 2 : 4-D with chloroacetic acid in presence of alkali. Both the reactions give good yields of the dichloro derivative.

The extensive use of dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2 : 4-D) as a selective herbicide has led to many attempts to synthesise this compound. Some of these consist in the direct conversion of phenoxyacetic acid into 2 : 4-D by nuclear chlorination. The methods of direct nuclear chlorination are due to Hopkins and Chisolm (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1946, 24B, 208) and Haskelberg (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 12, 426). These authors have used NaOCl solution and chlorine as the respective chlorinating agents in presence of Fe as catalyst. The yields obtained by the two different methods are respectively 75-80% and 82%. But repetition of the above experiments in our laboratory has failed to achieve the recorded percentage yield (the yield obtained being 60-66% in both the cases). This has led to the present investigation regarding other suitable chlorinating agents for the preparation of 2:4-D. It is known that certain cyclic compounds can be halogenated by the action of dichlorocarbamide. Chlorination of phenol by dichlorocarbamide was studied by Lickoschertsov (*Am. Chem. Abs.*, 1930, 24, 836). Thereby dichlorocarbamide has been attempted by the present author and found quite suitable for direct nuclear chlorination of phenoxyacetic acid. The method of preparation of dichlorocarbamide as described by Chattaway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 464) using zinc oxide being costly, various substitutes for zinc oxide have been attempted and freshly prepared aluminium hydroxide has been found most useful. Aluminium hydroxide is cheaper, it can be easily prepared and gives an yield near to that obtained by Chattaway (*loc. cit.*). In order to save time and reduce the manipulative effort the dichlorocarbamide is not isolated from the solution but is allowed to react *in situ* with the phenoxyacetic acid. The procedure thus becomes extremely simple.

The second method of preparation of 2 : 4-D consists in the preparation of 2 : 4-dichlorophenol, which is next condensed with chloroacetic acid in the presence of alkali (Pokorny, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1768). Several methods of preparation of 2 : 4-dichlorophenol are reported in the literature. Hoffeman (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1917, 37, 96) prepared 2 : 4-dichlorophenol by passing a current of chlorine gas into molten phenol until the requisite increase in weight took place and then by separating 2 : 4- and 2 : 6-dichlorophenols so formed. The method is very cumbrous and further 2 : 4-dichlorophenol cannot

be completely separated from 2 : 6-dichlorophenol. Chandon (Ber., 1893, 16, 1751) utilised 'sodium hypochlorite as a chlorinating agent in presence of a considerable amount of salicylic acid and caustic potash for the preparation of 2 : 4-dichlorophenol. The percentage yield, however, is not mentioned and the process suffers from the disadvantage of using salicylic acid, a costly material. The third method due to Clark (*Chem. News*, 1931., 143, 265) consists in the chlorination of phenol with trimethylacetyl chloride. Though the percentage yield, as claimed by the author, is very high (about 85%), the method is hardly advantageous on account of the difficulty in obtaining the chlorinating agent. In view of the difficulties encountered in the preparation of 2 : 4-dichlorophenol, a simpler method employing easily available starting materials has been devised. The method consists in the conversion of 2 : 4-dinitrophenol obtained by the nitration of phenol to 2 : 4-dichlorophenol through several steps. Phenol is nitrated by the process of Marquoyrol and Loriette (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1919, 25, 375) with certain modifications. Instead of using sulphuric acid of density 1.58 and completing the reaction by raising the temperature to 100° towards the end, as suggested by the above mentioned authors, a higher concentration of sulphuric acid (*d* 1.72) has been used and the reaction is completed at 75°-80° affording a 10% increase in yield over that obtained by Marquoyrol and Loriette (*loc. cit.*). The 2 : 4-dinitrophenol so obtained is then reduced to 2 : 4-diaminophenol hydrochloride with tin and HCl. 2 : 4-Diaminophenol hydrochloride is next diazotised and coupled with cuprous chloride by the standard method (Sandmeyer's reaction). The product thus formed is then steam distilled, when 2 : 4-dichlorophenol separates out from the distillate. The yield is quite satisfactory. The 2 : 4-dichlorophenol is next condensed with chloroacetic acid in presence of alkali giving a good yield of 2:4-D.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

First Method. Preparation of Dichlorocarbamide.—A solution of carbamide (6 g.) in 50 c. c. of water was taken in a three-necked flask, the central opening being closed by a cork. To the solution was added freshly prepared aluminium hydroxide (obtained from 32 g. of alum). The solution with the suspension of aluminium hydroxide was then cooled in a freezing mixture and a rapid stream of chlorine was passed through it, care being taken that the temperature of the reaction did not rise above 0° and the flask well shaken during the passage of the gas. Aluminium hydroxide quickly dissolved giving a clear solution and in a very short time the liquid became thickened with the separation of crystals of dichlorocarbamide. When no more crystals separated, the dichlorocarbamide was rapidly filtered in a pump, washed a few times with ice-cold distilled water and then finally dried by washing with dry chloroform. Dichlorocarbamide was obtained as white, crystalline powder, yield 9 g. (70% of the theoretical).

Preparation of 2:4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic Acid.—In the above method of preparation, when no more crystals of dichlorocarbamide appeared to separate, the current of chlorine was discontinued and phenoxyacetic acid (10 g.), obtained from sodium phenate (8.5 g.) and sodium chloroacetate (8.5 g.) with caustic soda as condensing agent, was added. The whole mass was then vigorously agitated for about 2 hours by means of a mechanical stirrer through the central neck with occasional addition of 10 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid during the entire period. A considerable amount of heat was evolved. The precipitate was then filtered, washed with cold water, and the 2:4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid was recrystallised from benzene, m. p. 138° yield 8.5 g. (55% of the theoretical). (Found : Cl, 32.25. Calc. Cl, 32.1 per cent).

Second Method. Preparation of 2:4-Dichlorophenol.—Phenol (9.4 g.) was nitrated with a mixture of H_2SO_4 (d 1.72, 40 c. c.) and HNO_3 (d 1.33, 20 c. c.) by the improved method, already referred to. The product on crystallisation from water gave colorless crystals of 2:4-dinitrophenol (yield 14.7 g., 80% of the theoretical). 2:4-Dinitrophenol (about 9 g.) was reduced in the usual way with tin and HCl (16 g. tin and 80 c. c. conc. HCl) to obtain 2:4-diaminophenol hydrochloride. 2:4-Diaminophenol hydrochloride (5 g.) was then diazotised with sodium nitrite (4.4 g.) solution. The well cooled diazotised solution was then coupled with cuprous chloride solution at a temperature lower than 5° by the standard method (Sandmeyer's reaction). The cuprous chloride solution was prepared by dissolving 3.3 g. copper carbonate in 33 c. c. of conc. HCl and heating the solution with excess of copper turnings. After coupling, the product was steam distilled when 2:4-dichlorophenol separated out from the distillate in needle-shaped crystals, m. p. 45°, yield 3.2 g. (78-80% of the theoretical).

Preparation of 2:4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic Acid.—2:4-Dichlorophenol and monochloroacetic acid in equimolecular proportions were heated in minimum quantity of water with a slight excess of caustic soda until the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. The dried mass was then washed several times with 95% alcohol and then acidified with an excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. The 2:4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, thus formed, was filtered, washed several times with ice-cold water and dried. It was purified by crystallisation from benzene, m. p. 138°. yield 85% of the theoretical. (Found : Cl, 32.3. Calc. Cl, 32.1 per cent).

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